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Preprint · December 2022

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The influence of a colour themed HMI on trust and take-over performance in automated vehicles

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2 ABSTRACT

3 SAE Level 3 is known as conditional driving automation. As long as certain conditions are
4 met, there is no need to supervise the technology and the driver can engage in non-driving
5 related tasks (NDRTs). However, a human driver must be present and alert to take over when
6 the automation is facing its system limits. When such an emergency takes place, the automation
7 uses the human machine interface (HMI) to send a take-over request (TOR) to the driver. We
8 investigated the influence of a colour themed HMI on the trust and take-over performance in
9 automated vehicles. Using a driving simulator, we tested 45 participants divided in 3 groups with a
10 baseline auditory HMI and two advanced colour themed HMIs consisting of a display and ambient
11 light with the colours red and blue. Trust in automation was assessed using questionnaires while
12 take-over performance was assessed through response time and success rate. Compared to
13 the baseline HMI, the colour themed HMI is more trustworthy and participants understood their
14 driving tasks better. Results show that the colour themed HMI is perceived as more pleasant
15 compared to the baseline HMI and leads to shorter reaction times. Red ambient light is seen as
16 more urging than blue but HMI colour did not significantly affect the general HMI perception and
17 TOR performance.

18 **Keywords:** Take-over request; Trust; Automated Driving; HMI; Driving simulator

1 INTRODUCTION

19 Development of Automated Vehicles (AV) has been the main focus of car manufacturers as well as tech
20 companies. It is envisioned that AV could replace human driving, which could reduce traffic accidents and
21 thus increase road safety. The implementation of AV could also benefit the “driver” by increasing comfort
22 and enabling use of the driving time for work or leisure (Kyriakidis et al., 2015). The adoption of AV in
23 day-to-day life is not only dependent on the performance of the automation. The ultimate goal for AV is to

24 be broadly adopted in society. For this to happen, AV have to be trusted and accepted by the public. Trust
25 is defined as "the attitude that an agent will help achieve an individual's goals in a situation characterised
26 by uncertainty and vulnerability" according to Lee and See (2004).

27 The main focus of this research will be on SAE level 3 automation, which is defined as "The sustained
28 and operational design domain (ODD) specific performance by an automated driving system (ADS) of
29 the entire dynamic driving task (DDT) with the expectation that the DDT fallback-ready user is receptive
30 to ADS-issued requests to intervene, as well as to DDT performance-relevant system failures in other
31 vehicle systems, and will respond appropriately" (SAE International, 2021). This means that when the
32 automation is activated, the driver could keep his eyes off the road and perform a non-driving-related task
33 (NDRT). When the automation reaches its limits, the automation requests the driver to take over control of
34 the vehicle. This request initiated by the vehicle is called a take-over request (TOR) (Lu et al., 2016).

35 The TOR is conveyed by the Human Machine Interface (HMI) of the AV. An HMI is a user interface
36 that relays information from a machine or system to a person (Stouffer et al., 2011). Several studies
37 ((Petermeijer et al., 2017; Politis et al., 2015; Naujoks et al., 2021)) have revealed effects of TOR modality
38 on performance. Kim et al. (2021) found that TOR presented only through the visual modality yielded the
39 longest reaction time, whereas adding the auditory modality reduced the reaction time. Extensive research
40 has been conducted on various elements in the HMI and often the result is that a more advanced HMI
41 outperforms a basic HMI in terms of trust as well as performance (Zhang et al., 2019). Forster et al. (2017)
42 showed that adding speech has a positive influence on trust. Sonoda and Wada (2017) showed that adding a
43 vibrotactile display has a positive influence on trust. Showing the TOR on a display tends to increase the
44 trust in the automation and the take-over performance (Löcken et al., 2020). In (Yang et al., 2018) adding a
45 LED bar to the HMI increased the take-over performance and trust in the automation.

46 Ambient lighting has a positive influence on, amongst others, perceived safety and interior functionality
47 (Caberletti et al., 2010). It provides information without demanding much cognitive workload and does not
48 distract users' from their primary tasks (Matthews et al., 2004). Due to these characteristics and the high
49 workload in a driving context, we studied the application of ambient lighting in automated vehicles. Several
50 researches have studied the effect of various design aspect of ambient lighting in automated vehicles.
51 Feierle et al. (2020) mounted ambient lighting in the steering wheel and windshield, and evaluated the
52 take-over performance. The results showed that there was no significant effect of the positions on take-over
53 performance. Borojeni et al. (2016) revealed that different ambient light patterns did not affect take-over
54 performance. An important aspect of visual HMI is the colour used to convey the TOR. Here colours like
55 red can convey the urgency and safety critical aspect of the TOR, while colours as blue would suggest a
56 lower urgency (Friedrich and Vollrath, 2022). A higher urgency can promote a rapid TOR response (Politis
57 et al., 2015) but may also induce high stress levels hampering trust, acceptance and take-over performance.

58 In most cases the colour of the lighting is assigned rather than researched. This gap led to our main
59 research question: *How does a colour themed HMI influence trust and take-over performance in AV?* The
60 objective of this paper is to investigate the safety as well as the trust the driver has in the AV with a colour
61 themed HMI.

62 In order to achieve the objective, tests were performed using a driving simulator. Different HMIs were used
63 to analyse the influence of different colours on the drivers trust and take-over performance.

64

2 METHODS

65 A colour themed HMI was designed including a display at the midconsole, ambient lighting and sound
66 and a basic HMI, which only uses sound, was used as baseline. The choices that led to the design of the
67 experiment are given below.

68 2.1 Participants

69 Forty-five participants were recruited via various channels to take part in this experiment, of which 14 were
70 female and 31 were male. All had at least two years of driving experience and were between 18 and 28
71 years old. The participants were evenly divided in three test groups based on Gender, Driving Experience
72 and results from the pre-trust in automation questionnaire. The group that was tested with a basic HMI that
73 is not colour themed was called “Baseline”. The group that was tested with the red themed HMI was called
74 “Red”. The last group that was tested with a blue themed HMI was called “Blue”.

75 2.2 Apparatus

76 This experiment took place at the intelligent vehicles group at the Delft University of Technology, and
77 was conducted using the Delft Advanced Vehicle Simulator (DAVSi) (Fig. 1) (Khusro et al., 2020). The
78 mock-up vehicle placed in the simulator, a 2013 Toyota Yaris, includes a driver and passenger seat. The
79 instrument cluster is functioning and shows the speed and the RPM of the vehicle. The projection screen
80 that shows the driving environment is placed in front of the mock-up vehicle and shows a 200° field of
81 view. IPG CarMaker 8.0.1 was used to generate the environment and traffic of the scenario. IPG movie was
82 used to display the graphics on the screen. The colour themed HMIs used a 10.9-inch display in the centre
83 console and ambient lighting to show the TOR request (Fig. 2a & 2b). A smartphone on the left side of the
84 steering wheel was used for the NDRT (Fig. 2a & 2b). The ambient lighting consisted of multiple led strips
85 controlled by an Arduino receiving commands from DAVSi via a series port. The IPG driver model was
86 used to realise automated driving. During take-over drivers were expected to control speed by braking.

87 2.3 HMIs

88 Three different HMIs were designed and used in the experiment. The HMI of the baseline group consisted
89 of only an auditory interface, in which no ambient lighting or display was shown during a TOR. The HMI
90 of the colour themed groups consisted of the same auditory and a visual interface as shown in Table 2 and
91 in Fig. 2a & 2b.

92 2.3.1 Auditory interface

93 There were two transition-related sounds in the vehicle (see supplementary material). When the AV issued
94 a TOR, a short sound of 1.5 s was repeated until the driver intervened. This sound is called 'TOR-sound'.
95 As the driver was engaging in an NDRT and was visually distracted, the TOR sound was expected to be the
96 first TOR sign that would be noticed by the participant. When the AV resumed automated driving after the
97 TOR, a short sound has been played for 1.5 s. This sound is called 'automation-start-sound'. After hearing
98 this sound the driver was expected to continue with the NDRT as the automation took back control. The
99 two sounds were designed for informing AV activation and requesting take-over. Alarm levels, usefulness,
100 and appropriateness with situations of the two sounds were validated in our previous study (Kim et al.,
101 2022). Results have shown that the two sounds were appropriately designed for their driving context.

102 2.3.2 Visual interface

103 *Colour:* The three different HMIs could be distinguished by the presence and colour of a visual HMI and
104 ambient light. The basic HMI used sound only. The other two HMIs, used the colours red and blue in both
105 the HMI display and as ambient light. In general, a red colour, which has a large wavelength, stimulates
106 physical performance (Hill and Barton, 2005). This indicates that red would be beneficial for the reaction
107 time. On the other hand, red undermines cognitive performance and blue is perceived as more calming and
108 trustworthy (Elliot et al., 2007). This indicates that blue colours, which have a smaller wavelength, let the
109 driver be more comfortable and relaxed, which would lead to a more calm and safe take-over.

110 *Display:* For the colour themed HMIs, the visual TOR was shown on the mid-console display. A drawing
111 of a brake pedal together with the text "Brake" indicated that the participant had to take over control by
112 braking.

113 *Light:* For the colour themed HMIs, ambient lighting was added on several points in the interior, below
114 eyesight, so that the driver could notice the lights without getting distracted or blinded. The red themed
115 HMI contained red ambient lighting and the blue themed HMI contained blue ambient lighting (Fig. 2a &
116 2b).

117 Both the display and the ambient light were activated at the start of each TOR and remained active until
118 the automation took back control.

119 2.4 Scenario

120 The driving scenario had 8 separate situations which took place on a highway. The drive was initiated with
121 SAE level 3 automation, starting from standstill and accelerating to the speed limit which is 100 km/h in
122 most parts and 130 km/h in others (Fig. 3). The 8 situations can be subdivided into two categories, system
123 manoeuvres and TORs. The system manoeuvres were handled by the automation. The TORs were to be
124 handled by the participant, where in all TOR braking was the appropriate intervention. However, when
125 participants did not brake in time, the automation intervened if the time to collision (TTC) became less
126 than 2 seconds, and prevented collisions. To ensure that the participants would not be confused by the
127 situations, a distinction between system manoeuvres and TORs has been made. Take-over situations only
128 included braking (speed control) while system manoeuvres included steering. During the whole scenario,
129 there was foggy weather with a visibility of 300 m. This created a somewhat more critical situation to test
130 trust in automation. However, the 300 m always enabled timely visual detection of other vehicles well
131 before the TOR.

132 The first phase of the scenario was designed to make the participants acquainted with the simulator, the
133 automation and the TOR. This phase consisted of two system manoeuvres. Following this phase, the first
134 and second TOR took place. After these TORs, the third system manoeuvre, the third TOR, the fourth
135 system manoeuvre and the fourth TOR took place respectively (Fig. 3). In the next sections, the system
136 manoeuvres and TORs will be explained in detail. To minimise the influence of one situation on the other,
137 there was a minimum of 3 minutes in between every traffic situation. Whenever the AV was in automated
138 state, the participant had to engage in an NDRT, which was playing Angry bird, a visual-motor task without
139 sound, on a mounted device. The NDRT is self-paced and interruptible, so participants could pause it
140 whenever necessary to check the surrounding (Naujoks et al., 2017).

141 2.4.1 System manoeuvres

142 There were three types of system manoeuvres.

- 143 • The ego vehicle overtakes a vehicle driving slower on the right lane in System Manoeuvre 1 and 4 (Fig.
144 4a).
- 145 • The ego vehicle overtakes a vehicle suddenly merging in front from the insertion lane in System
146 Manoeuvre 2 (Fig. 4b).
- 147 • Steering of the ego vehicle to make it follow the curvature of the road in System Manoeuvre 3.

148 2.4.2 TORs

149 In total there were four TORs where a sudden change of events caused the AV to request a TOR.

- 150 • The first TOR (TOR 1 in Fig. 3) took place on a two-lane road. The ego car had a constant speed of
151 100 km/h for 2 km before the automation suddenly noticed that the traffic car in front of the ego car
152 was braking. The distance to the traffic car was around 100 m and even though there was a left lane, an
153 overtake was no option because of multiple cars passing on the left lane with a speed of 110 km/h (Fig.
154 4c). Therefore, the ego-car driver had to take over control and achieve hard braking. After braking,
155 the traffic car in front of the ego car had a speed of 40 km/h which resulted in the ego car eventually
156 overtaking the traffic car.
- 157 • The second TOR (TOR 2 in Fig. 3) took place on a piece of road where two lanes merged into one
158 (Fig. 4d). The ego car was driving on the right lane and there was a traffic car driving in front of it.
159 As the end of the left lane approached, a traffic car on the left lane tried to overtake the traffic car in
160 front of the ego car (Fig. 4d). The traffic car was forced to brake suddenly to a speed of 50 km/h and
161 the automation requested a TOR. The distance to the traffic car in front was around 80 meters, and
162 an overtake was no option because of the merging left lane. The ego-car driver had to achieve hard
163 braking to prevent an accident. After the TOR, the traffic car accelerated to a speed of 110 km/h.
- 164 • The third TOR (TOR 3 in Fig. 3) took place on a one-lane road. The ego car encountered a traffic jam
165 (Fig. 4e). The distance to the traffic car in front was around 150 m, and an overtake was not possible as
166 there was no left lane. The only safe outcome was achieved by hard braking. After the TOR, the traffic
167 cars accelerated to a speed of 115 km/h, leaving the ego car behind.
- 168 • The fourth and last TOR (TOR 4 in Fig. 3) took place on a two-lane road. Just like the previous TOR,
169 the ego car encountered a traffic jam (Fig. 4f). The distance to the traffic car in front was around 150 m.
170 An overtake was not possible as there was a traffic jam on the left lane too. The ego-car driver had to
171 achieve hard-braking. After the TOR, the traffic cars accelerated to a speed of 115 km/h, leaving the
172 ego car behind.

173

174 2.5 Procedure

175 Each participant had to read an instruction with information about the steps that would take place before,
176 during and after the simulator drive. After this instruction, the participants were asked to fill in a pre-drive
177 questionnaire, which contained an explanation about SAE Level 3 automation (Table 1). The pre-drive
178 questionnaire was used to test the familiarity and trust of the participant regarding SAE level 3 automation
179 before taking part in the research, and was used to create balanced participant groups for the 3 HMIs.
180 Filling in the pre-drive questionnaire took about 10 minutes. After finishing the pre-drive questionnaire
181 the participants took place in the simulator. The participants went through the designed scenario which
182 took around 30 minutes to finish. During the simulator drive, two questions were asked after each TOR.
183 After finishing the drive, participants were asked to fill in a post-drive questionnaire which took about 15

184 minutes to finish (Table 3). The post-drive questionnaire was used to measure the trust in the automation
185 after having experienced the automation. The whole process took around 50-60 minutes per participant.

186 **2.6 Measurements**

187 Objective measurements of driver performance were gained during the simulator drive while subjective
188 measurements were obtained through pre-drive and post-drive questionnaires, and questions asked during
189 the drive after each TOR.

190 **2.6.1 Objective measurement**

191 The objective data can be divided into two groups, the take-over time and take-over quality. The take-over
192 time was measured by the reaction time, between the initiation of the TOR and the first brake or gas input
193 from the participant (Gold et al., 2013). The take-over quality was measured by the percentage of successful
194 TORs. A TOR was considered successful if the automation did not intervene by braking (automation
195 intervened if the TTC became less than 2 seconds).

196 **2.6.2 Subjective measurement**

197 The pre-drive questionnaire (Table 1) was used to assess participants' earlier experiences with AV (G1),
198 their initial thoughts on trust and acceptance in AV (G2) and willingness to perform NDRT in AV (G3).

199 During the simulator drive, the participant were asked two questions after each TOR:

200 *G11 - How stressful was this TOR on a scale from 1 to 5?*

201 *G12 - How urgent was this TOR on a scale from 1 to 5?*

202 The data gathered from these questions were used to assess the take-over perception of the participants. The
203 questions were asked directly after each TOR so the participants had a clear memory of their perception.

204 The post-drive questionnaire (Table 3) filled in after the simulator drive has been used to obtain the
205 participants' thoughts on the automation as experienced. The advantage of having pre- and post-drive
206 questionnaires is that apart from drawing conclusions on the absolute trust in automation, conclusions
207 about the increase in trust can be drawn.

3 RESULTS

208 All participants completed the full experiment, responded adequately to most TORs, and did not intervene
209 in the automated system manoeuvres. Results with the three HMIs are presented in Tables 4-6 and in
210 Figures 5-8 placed in the discussion. Results for question groups are presented as an average over items in
211 each question group (see Tables 1 and 3). Before averaging, items representing negative perceptions were
212 reverse coded ('How dangerous are SAE Level 3 automated vehicles', 'The system is deceptive', 'The user
213 interface is complex').

214 Results show clear positive effects of the presence of the colour themed visual HMIs with few effects
215 of HMI colour. The significance of these effects was evaluated using three p-values. The p_{BC} value,
216 calculated with a two-sample t-test, compares the baseline group with the two colour themed HMIs
217 combined, to evaluate the difference between the simple auditory and the more advanced HMIs. The p_{RB}
218 value, also calculated with a two-sample t-test, compares the red group with the blue group, to assess the
219 effect of HMI colour. The p_{all} value, calculated with a one-way ANOVA, compares the three individual
220 groups, to assess the significance of any differences between the three HMIs. For these statistical tests, a

221 significance threshold of $\alpha = 0,05$ was used. Post-hoc paired-samples t-tests using Bonferroni correction
222 were performed (with an adjusted $\alpha = 0.05/3 = 0.0167$) for pairwise comparisons.

223 Questions G2 and G3 from the pre-drive questionnaire were used to create balanced participant groups
224 for the three HMIs. This was successful as differences between groups for G2 and G3 were insignificant
225 (see Table 4).

226 **3.1 Trust and HMI experience**

227 Table 4 shows pre-drive and post-drive questionnaire responses for the three HMIs. The post-drive
228 questionnaire shows substantial benefits of the colour themed HMIs for G4-G9. These benefits are
229 significant for all question groups except for G7. However in G4-G9 no significant differences are found
230 between the blue themed and red themed HMI. The only significant effect of HMI colour is the ambient
231 colour perception (G10) where, as expected, red was perceived as much more urging (3.92) compared to
232 blue (2.07) on a scale from 1-5. However, this higher urgency associated with ambient colour did not have
233 negative or positive effects on the overall perception of trust and HMI (G4-G9). This demonstrates that
234 both colour themed HMIs significantly enhanced the automation experience and trust and that these HMIs
235 were positively evaluated. However these subjective benefits of the colour themed HMIs did not differ
236 between the red and blue themed HMIs.

237 **3.2 Take-over perception**

238 After each TOR, every participant was asked questions about their perception of the TOR. Since the urgency
239 and stress per TOR is not relevant for this paper, the results of the four TORs were averaged per HMI
240 group and are stated in Table 5. The colour themed HMIs induced a significantly higher urgency and stress
241 ($p_{BC} = .042$). The p_{RB} values however are very high ($> .6$) which indicates that differences between red
242 and blue are insignificant. Thus both colour themed HMIs create a similar TOR urgency and stress in G11
243 and G12 even though the ambient colour red was perceived as more urging in G10.

244 **3.3 Take-over performance**

245 Table 7 shows the TOR reaction time. TOR data of 4 participants were not saved. With the first and fourth
246 TOR, two participants did not react and thus no reaction time was collected. The second and third TOR
247 had three participants which did not react. This missing data was not taken into account in any calculations
248 of reaction time. The colour themed HMIs reduced the TOR reaction time in TOR1-TOR4 and this effect
249 was significant for TOR1, TOR3 and the average over TOR1-TOR4. The red themed HMI reduced the
250 reaction time with an average of 0.42 s against baseline whereas the blue themed HMI reduced the reaction
251 time with only 0.15 s. However this difference between red and blue themed HMIs was not significant
252 ($p_{RB}=.156$). The quality of the take-over is measured by the success rate. This is a percentage that shows
253 how many takeovers where completed without any intervention of the automation. This success rate is
254 shown in Table 6 and indicates that the automation intervened in a majority of TORs. Apparently the
255 time-window offered to react was rather short while the perceived urgency to intervene was modest (the
256 urgency was around 3 on a scale from 1-5 : see G11 in Table 5). This only emerged analysing all results.
257 The majority of the participants thought they were handling the take-over themselves, while in reality it
258 was the automation that intervened. This problem was most apparent with the baseline HMI, whereas the
259 transition between manual and automated driving was more clear for the colour themed HMIs since the
260 ambient lighting turned off when the automation took over. The red themed HMI led to most successful
261 TORs but effects of HMI on TOR quality were not significant.

4 DISCUSSION

263 This study investigated the influence of a colour themed HMI on trust and take-over performance in
 264 an automated vehicle. 45 participants were divided in three groups, each with a different HMI. Every
 265 participant had to perform four TORs in a 30-minute drive, during which their performance was measured.
 266 Before, during and after the drive, participants filled in questionnaires to assess their increase in trust.

267 4.1 Trust and HMI experience

268 With all three HMIs trust in automation was higher after the experiment (Fig. 5) and this trust increase was
 269 significantly higher with the colour themed HMIs. While the trust of the baseline group only increased
 270 with 0,35, the trust of the red and blue themed HMI groups increased with 0,73 and 0,74, respectively.
 271 Furthermore, the colour themed HMIs scored significantly better on 'Trust Process (G6)', 'Trust purpose
 272 (G7)', 'HMI Driving task (G8)' and 'HMI Feeling (G9)' and this effect was significant for G6, G8 and
 273 G9. These positive effects of the informative visual HMI and ambient light align with (Zhang et al., 2019;
 274 Löcken et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2018).

275 4.2 Take-over perception

276 With the colour themed HMIs the TORs were perceived as more urgent and more stressful as compared
 277 to the baseline HMI (Fig. 7). The higher urgency can be seen as positive and the higher stress is not
 278 alarming with a mean around 2.7 on a scale from 1-5. However the higher stress could be associated with
 279 the additional information to be processed with the advanced HMIs.

280 4.3 Take-over performance

281 Regarding the take-over performance (G13, G14, G15, G16, G17) in Fig. 8, two results stand out. The
 282 reaction times in the first TOR are significantly higher in comparison to the following TORs with all three
 283 HMIs. This indicates that participants were learning how to react to the TORs, which is a common finding
 284 (Gold et al., 2018). The red themed HMI elicited the shortest reaction times in all four TORs. This reaction
 285 time benefit was significant comparing the colour themed HMIs to baseline but the difference between red
 286 and blue was not significant.

287 The percentage of successful TORs (G18) indicates that the automation intervened in a majority of cases.
 288 This could have been alleviated through an even earlier TOR which however may not always be technically
 289 feasible. This could also be alleviated through a later but more aggressive intervention by the automation.
 290 In our study the automation intervened if the TTC became less than 2 seconds. However this is overly
 291 conservative as TCC ignores accelerations. This could be resolved using the enhanced time to collision
 292 (ETTC) to control the intervention. ETTC takes in consideration the deceleration of both vehicles, which is
 293 relevant in our scenario (Happee et al., 2017).

$$TTC = \frac{dx}{v} \quad (1)$$

$$ETTC = \begin{cases} \frac{dx}{v} & , \text{if } a = 0 \\ \frac{v - \sqrt{v^2 + 2a * dx}}{-a} & , \text{if } a \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

295 **4.4 Marginal effects of HMI colour**

296 The difference between the baseline and the colour themed HMIs is substantial across a majority of results
297 which demonstrates the ability of the selected experimental conditions and measures to assess the benefits
298 of HMIs to enhance human performance and perception in automated driving. The differences between
299 the red and blue themed HMIs however, are small. The only significant difference between red and blue
300 regards the ambient colour perception (G10) (Table 4). While red is perceived as urging, blue tends to be a
301 more calming colour (e.g. Elliot et al. (2007)). Expected benefits of the red interface were insignificant in
302 the current data but showed the expected trend with shorter reaction times (G13-G17) and more successful
303 TORs (G18) with the red interface.

304 **4.5 Recommendations**

305 We tested 3 groups of participants between 18 and 28 years old with at least 2 years of driving experience.
306 Driving experience is a key factor in both trust and safe driving performance (Jin et al., 2020) and age
307 affects risk perception and driving skill. The limited sample size may explain the insignificance of several
308 effects of HMI colour. Testing a larger and broader population sample is recommended to further establish
309 benefits of colour themed HMIs. Herein also other colours and combinations of multimodal TOR HMIs
310 can be explored. The range of scenarios can be expanded and HMIs can be tested in actual vehicles on
311 tracks and public roads.

312 This driving simulator study demonstrates significant benefits of a colour themed HMI:

- 313 • The advanced colour themed HMI with display and ambient light contributes more to the trust in
314 automated vehicles in comparison to the baseline auditory HMI. Participants found the colour themed
315 HMI more trustworthy, they understood their driving tasks better and they found the HMI more pleasant
316 to work with.
- 317 • The advanced colour themed HMI outperforms the baseline HMI in case of TOR. Participants who
318 experienced the colour themed HMI found that the TORs were more urgent and stressful, which led to
319 a reduced reaction time.
- 320 • The red ambient light is perceived as more urging while blue is perceived as calming, but effects of
321 colour on TOR performance and trust were not significant.

322 The obtained results could contribute to acceptance of automated vehicles. An advanced colour themed
323 HMI can improve trust in automated vehicles and contribute to safety in TOR.

5 CONCLUSIONS

324 This driving simulator study demonstrates significant benefits of a colour themed HMI:

- 325 • The advanced colour themed HMI with display and ambient light contributes more to the trust in
326 automated vehicles in comparison to the baseline auditory HMI. Participants found the colour themed
327 HMI more trustworthy, they understood their driving tasks better and they found the HMI more pleasant
328 to work with.
- 329 • The advanced colour themed HMI outperforms the baseline HMI in case of TOR. Participants who
330 experienced the colour themed HMI found that the TORs were more urgent and stressful, which led to
331 a reduced reaction time.

332 • The red ambient light is perceived as more urging while blue is perceived as calming, but effects of
333 colour on TOR performance and trust were not significant.

334 The obtained results could contribute to acceptance of automated vehicles. An advanced colour themed
335 HMI can improve trust in automated vehicles and contribute to safety in TOR.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

336 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
337 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

338 **Aboubakr el Jouhri, Ashraf el Sharkawy, Hakan Paksoy, and Omar Youssif:** Conceptualization, Data
339 curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Xiaolin He,**
340 **Soyeon Kim, and Riender Happee:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review and
341 editing.

FUNDING

342 Soyeon Kim and Riender Happee are supported by the HADRIAN European Union’s Horizon 2020
343 research and innovation program (grant agreement 875597), and Xiaolin He is supported by the SHAPE-
344 IT European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant
345 agreement 860410). The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not
346 necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

347 We want to thank Dr. Barys Shyrokau and Joris Giltay for their support using the DAVSi driving simulator.

SUPPLEMENTAL DATA

348 Supplementary material: 2 sounds representing the auditory cues and 1 video recording the whole
349 experiment process.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

350 The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article, further inquiries can be directed
351 to the corresponding author.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS AND TABLES

Figure 1. DAVSi driving simulator

Figure 2a. Red themed HMI

Figure 2b. Blue themed HMI

Figure 2. Two colour-themed HMIs with ambient lighting, HMI display at the midconsole and NDRT left of the steer.

Figure 3. Road map of the scenario

Figure 4a. System Manoeuvre 1 and 4 (ego car (blue) is overtaking a slower moving traffic car (orange))

Figure 4b. System Manoeuvre 2 (ego car (blue) is changing lanes to create space for a merging traffic car (orange))

Figure 4c. TOR 1 (Traffic car (red) brakes hard, ego car (blue) cannot change to the left lane due to the traffic cars (orange), so a TOR is initiated. The participant is expected to brake.)

Figure 4d. TOR 2 (Traffic car (orange) cuts off the red traffic car, the traffic car (red) brakes which leads to a TOR for the driver which is represented by the ego car (blue))

Figure 4e. TOR 3 (Traffic jam on a one-lane road caused by stationary traffic cars (orange), traffic car (red) brakes which results in a TOR for the ego car (blue))

Figure 4f. TOR 4 (Traffic jam on a two-lane road caused by stationary traffic cars (traffic), traffic car (red) brakes which results in a TOR for the ego car (blue))

Figure 4. System manoeuvres and take over requests

Figure 5. Trust increase visualised by the pre-drive trust in automation G2, post-drive trust G5, trust process G6, and trust purpose G7 (mean ratings with standard deviations).

Figure 6. HMI driving task G8 and HMI feeling G9 (mean ratings with standard deviations).

Figure 7. TOR perception of urgency G11 and stress G12 (mean ratings with standard deviations).

Figure 8. TOR reaction times G17 (in s) for every TOR (means with standard deviations).

Group	Question
G1 - Automation experience	-Have you ever experienced Adaptive Cruise Control? -Have you ever experienced Lane-Assist? -Have you ever experienced a combination of Adaptive Cruise Control and Lane-assist? -Have you ever experienced Tesla’s Auto-pilot?
G2 - Trust in automation	-How safe would you feel in an SAE LEVEL 3 automated vehicle? -Are SAE Level 3 automated vehicles dangerous? (Reverse coded) -To what extent would you trust an SAE Level 3 automated vehicle? -Would you feel fine handing over control to an SAE level 3 Automated Vehicle?
G3 - NDRT	-To what extent are you willing to do Non-Driving Related Tasks, such as using your phone, while using the driving automation system?

Table 1. Pre-drive questionnaire divided in three Groups. Participants could rate every question from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

HMI	Baseline	Red	Blue
Auditory	Generic sounds	Generic sounds	Generic sounds
Lighting	None	Red ambient lighting	Blue ambient lighting
Display	None		

Table 2. Overview of the different HMIs

Group	Question	Source
G4 - Experience with automation	-The system's performance matches my expectations of an automated vehicle.	modified after Forster et al. (2017)
G5 - Trust in automation	-I trust the system to safely operate in the next drive. -I am convinced of the system. -The system is safe. -The system is dangerous. (Reverse coded) -The system is trustworthy. -The system is working accurately.	Gold et al. (2013) modified after Forster et al. (2017) Verberne et al. (2012) Gold et al. (2013) modified after Verberne et al. (2012)
G6 - Trust process	-I am familiar with the system. -I trust the system to warn me in time before a take-over situation. -The system is deceptive. (Reverse coded) -I trust the system during system maneuvers.	Jian et al. (2000) New item Jian et al. (2000) modified after Forster et al. (2017)
G7 - Trust purpose	-I feel fine handing over control to the system. -The system is a reliable partner. -The vehicle seems to be intelligent.	Waytz et al. (2014) Forster et al. (2017) Waytz et al. (2014)
G8 - HMI Driving task	-I would prefer more communication from the system. (Reverse coded) -My driving tasks during a take-over were clear. -The information provided by the user interface is sufficient. -The user interface clearly conveyed if the automation was working or not.	New item modified after Forster et al. (2017) New item New item
G9 - HMI Feeling	-The user interface is calming. -The user interface is comprehensible. -The user interface is complex. (Reverse coded) -The user interface is predictable.	New item New item New item New item
G10 - Ambient colour urgency Perception	-How did the colour of the ambient lighting make you feel? (scale from 1 (calming) to 5 (urging))	New item

Table 3. Post-drive questionnaire divided in groups with their corresponding references. Participants could rate every question from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Question group	HMI	M	SD	p-values
G2 - Pre-trust in automation	Baseline	2,82	0,65	$p_{BC}=0,837$
	Red	2,96	0,57	$p_{RB}=0,460$
	Blue	2,79	0,67	$p_{all}=0,758$
G3 - Pre-NDRT	Baseline	2,53	1,19	$p_{BC}=0,561$
	Red	3,00	1,36	$p_{RB}=0,316$
	Blue	2,53	1,13	$p_{all}=0,516$
G4 - Experience with automation	Baseline	3,20	0,68	$p_{BC}=0,003$
	Red	4,00	0,96	$p_{RB}=1,00$
	Blue	3,93	0,96	$p_{all}=0,027$
G5 - Trust in automation	Baseline	3,17	0,50	$p_{BC}=0,016$
	Red	3,69	0,60	$p_{RB}=0,529$
	Blue	3,53	0,74	$p_{all}=0,066$
(G5-G2) - Trust increase	Baseline	0,35	0,57	$p_{BC}=0,016$
	Red	0,73	1,25	$p_{RB}=0,529$
	Blue	0,74	1,05	$p_{all}=0,066$
G6 - Trust Process	Baseline	3,25	0,35	$p_{BC}=0,007$
	Red	3,64	0,66	$p_{RB}=0,905$
	Blue	3,62	0,51	$p_{all}=0,062$
G7 - Trust Purpose	Baseline	3,27	0,66	$p_{BC}=0,113$
	Red	3,67	0,64	$p_{RB}=0,569$
	Blue	3,53	0,63	$p_{all}=0,225$
G8 - HMI Driving Task	Baseline	2,58	0,50	$p_{BC}=0,001$
	Red	3,32	0,78	$p_{RB}=0,911$
	Blue	3,35	0,60	$p_{all}=0,002$
G9 - HMI Feeling	Baseline	2,80	0,60	$p_{BC}=0,001$
	Red	3,46	0,47	$p_{RB}=0,677$
	Blue	3,53	0,43	$p_{all}=0,0003$
G10 - Ambient colour urgency Perception	Red	3,92	0,95	$p_{RB}=0,001$
	Blue	2,07	0,80	

Table 4. Summary of the pre-drive and post-drive questionnaire data. Means and standard deviations were calculated for every HMI along with the corresponding p-values.

Question group	HMI	M	SD	p-values
G11 - TOR Urgency	Baseline	2,73	0,73	$p_{BC}=0,042$
	Red	3,16	0,79	$p_{RB}=0,613$
	Blue	3,32	0,88	$p_{all}=0,024$
G12 - TOR Stress	Baseline	2,15	0,70	$p_{BC}=0,036$
	Red	2,64	0,74	$p_{RB}=0,829$
	Blue	2,70	0,71	$p_{all}=0,010$

Table 5. Summary of the questionnaire responses on the take-over perception asked after each TOR. Means and standard deviations were calculated for every HMI along with the corresponding p-values.

	Baseline	Red	Blue	p-values
G18 - Percentage Successful TORs	7,5	26	11,25	$p_{BC}=0,060$ $p_{RB}=0,892$ $p_{all}=0,289$

Table 6. Percentage of successful TOR results for every HMI.

TOR number	HMI	M [s]	SD [s]	p-values
G13 - TOR 1 reaction time	Baseline	4,07	0,72	$p_{BC}=0,046$ $p_{RB}=0,364$ $p_{all}=0,097$
	Red	3,32	0,80	
	Blue	3,64	0,84	
G14 - TOR 2 reaction time	Baseline	3,08	0,80	$p_{BC}=0,063$ $p_{RB}=0,532$ $p_{all}=0,112$
	Red	2,46	0,60	
	Blue	2,63	0,74	
G15 - TOR 3 reaction time	Baseline	3,20	0,60	$p_{BC}=0,015$ $p_{RB}=0,304$ $p_{all}=0,033$
	Red	2,45	0,82	
	Blue	2,80	0,82	
G16 - TOR 4 reaction time	Baseline	2,95	0,76	$p_{BC}=0,063$ $p_{RB}=0,060$ $p_{all}=0,029$
	Red	2,17	0,58	
	Blue	2,70	0,77	
G17 - Average TOR reaction time	Baseline	3,23	0,47	$p_{BC}=0,023$ $p_{RB}=0,156$ $p_{all}=0,022$
	Red	2,81	0,60	
	Blue	3,08	0,77	

Table 7. Summary of the reaction time (in seconds) for every HMI. Means and standard deviations were calculated for every HMI along with the corresponding p-values.